

DIVINATION AND MENTAL HEALTH SEEKING BEHAVIOUR OF THE IBIBIO PEOPLE OF SOUTHERN NIGERIA: A QUALITATIVE EXPLORATION

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ABSTRACT

This research work examined divination and mental health seeking behaviour of Ibibio People in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The researcher made use of Mental Health Seeking Behaviour Model (MHSBM). Ibibio-speaking local government areas were purposively selected, and clustered into the 3 existing senatorial districts. Study participants were randomly selected from 16 Ibibio clans from randomly selected Ibibio-speaking local government areas. Study participants were engaged in interviews and their socio-demographic data collected were also presented with respective narratives. The findings of the study were analyzed qualitatively in thematic analysis with excerpts from the study participants. The findings of the study revealed that Ibibio people have a great belief that mental illness is spiritually influenced and priority is given to treatment with spiritual powers which diviners are usually patronized in terms of mental health services. It was concluded that divination become the preferred option for knowing the cause of the mental illness and for the control of the spirit in order to subject the patient to effective treatment; and most of the Ibibio people chose not to go to psychiatric hospitals for treatments to avoid the cultural implication of stigmatization which also contributes to the high dependency on divination and other forms of treatments. The researchers among others recommended that the Ibibio people should be educated on the causes of mental health and illnesses in order to reduce the stigmatization among the people and encourage patronage of psychiatric hospitals throughout Akwa Ibom State.

KEYWORDS: Mental illness, divination, Ibibio people, and health-seeking behaviour

INTRODUCTION

Positive mental health is linked to a range of development outcomes and is fundamental to coping with adversity, while poor mental health impedes an individual's capacity to realize their potential, work productively, and contribute to their community (World Health Organization 2012, cited in Azeem 2014). Every human being is a constitution of both mental and physical states and the health and wellbeing of any individual is ultimately dependent on the inter-relationship that exist between the physical and mental health (Kolappa *et al*, 2013). The disharmony between the mental and physical states results in a condition called mental illness, and mental illness, also called mental disorder or psychiatric illness is a disorder characterized by psychological symptoms, abnormal behaviours, impaired functioning or any combination of these (American Psychological Association APA, 2005).

Mental illness is said to refer to a wide range of mental health disorders that affect the mood, thinking, behaviour and one's ability to function in social, work or family activities (APA, 2018 cited in Esen and Peters, 2023^a). Mental health disorders according to Jack-Ide, Uys and Middleton (2013) constitute the major causes of disabilities worldwide, accounting for 37% of all healthy life years lost through disease. It is also universal, affecting people of all countries and societies, regardless of age, gender and income (Esen and Peters, 2023^a). The prevalence of mental illness in the adult population at any given time is about 10% and similarly, around 20% of all patients seen by primary health care providers have one or more mental health disorders (Cuijpers and Stam 2003). Mental health according to Stein (2013) cited in Esen and Peters (2023^b) could be seen as the successful performance of mental functions resulting in productive activities, fulfilling relationships, and the ability to adapt to change and cope with adversity. The reverse is mental illness.

Mental illness is considered to be a clinical significant behavioural or psychological syndrome experienced by a person and marked by distress, disability or the risk of suffering disability or loss of freedom (Mohr, 2003). Mental health could be characterised by alterations in reasoning, emotional mood or behaviour that is capable of causing distress, impaired ability to function or both (Esen and Peters 2023^b). Stein *et al*, (2010) defined mental illness as a psychological syndrome or pattern which is associated with distress (e.g. via a painful symptom), disability (impairment in one or more important areas of functioning), increased risk of death, or causes a significant loss of autonomy; however it excludes normal responses such as grief from loss of a loved one, and also excludes deviant behaviour for political, religious, or societal reasons not arising from a dysfunction in the individual. Mental illness as defined by Mental Health Association in Forsyth County (2009) is a disease of the brain that causes mild to severe disturbances in thought processes and/or behaviour, resulting in an inability to cope with life's ordinary demands and routines. Mental Health Association (2009) posit that there are more than 200 classified forms of mental illness. Some of the more common disorders are: clinical depression, bipolar disorder, dementia, schizophrenia and anxiety disorders (Esen and Peters, 2023^b). Mental illness according to Mental Health Association (2009) therefore involves expression of distress, an inability to be independent as well as alteration of mood, behaviour or thought due to a malfunctioning of a certain human organ responsible for these or any of these.

Regarding the nature, causes, and treatments of mental health issues, various societies throughout the world have different explanations (Ahmed *et al.*, 2015). These viewpoints are the outcome of specific societal cultural practices that are deeply ingrained in people's reasoning, behaviour, and speech (Esen and Peters, 2023^c). As the most suitable foundation for the creation of mental health programs, the community's role in the prevention and care of the mentally handicapped is now widely acknowledged (Kabir *et al.*, 2004). Numerous studies have demonstrated that understanding how the general public views mental illness and its treatment is a crucial first step toward the implementation of effective community-based programmes (Esen and Peters, 2023^b). The understanding, treatment, and management of mental health disorders are greatly influenced by the norms, beliefs, and practices of the person's cultural surroundings (Kabir *et al.*, 2004).

According to Shaikh and Hatcher (2005), a community's health-seeking behaviour influences how health services are used, which in turn affects population health outcomes. According to Subhudi (2015), up to 70% to 80% of mentally ill people live in rural areas, visit places of worship first, and seek treatment from indigenous practitioners. Factors influencing health-seeking behaviour can be political, cultural, socioeconomic, or physical. Indeed, cultural norms, economic conditions, and educational attainment can all have an impact on how a person uses the healthcare system (Esen and Peters, 2023^c). Additional variables include the surrounding environment, socio-demographic characteristics, and one's understanding of the healthcare system, gender issues, political climate, and facilities (Ogunlesi and Olanrewaju, 2010). There has been little research conducted in the South Southern region of Nigeria, but research on health seeking behaviour during mental illness has been conducted in several other parts of the world. There is ample evidence of how those who are mentally ill and their loved ones tackle mental illness in an attempt to find relief or a cure. It is commonly known, according to Adewuya and Makanjuola (2009) that sub-Saharan Africa lacks access to timely and efficient professional mental health services, which are necessary to prevent chronic illness and the development of irreversible sequelae.

Similarly, Burns and Tomita (2015) noted that a lack of appropriate infrastructure, human resources, and treatment options contributes to a significant treatment gap for mental health in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs). The World Health Organization's Atlas Project on mental health data reveals widespread, systematic, and long-term neglect of resources for mental health care in low-income and middle-income countries; nowhere is this more evident than on the African continent (Burns and Tomita, 2015). Similarly, Burns and Tomita (2015) noted that a lack of appropriate infrastructure, human resources, and treatment options contributes to a significant treatment gap for mental health in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs). The World Health Organization's Atlas Project on mental health data reveals widespread, systematic, and long-term neglect of resources for mental health care in low-income and middle-income countries; nowhere is this more evident than on the African continent (Burns and Tomita, 2015).

Researchers have found relative levels of efficacy on the perceived efficacy of traditional and alternative mental health care, which may have maintained their belief and patronage in low-income countries. According to Abbo (2011), who examined the results and profiles of traditional healing practices for severe mental illnesses in two districts of Eastern Uganda, there was a general trend in the symptom scales of a cohort of patients with severe

mental illness who saw traditional healers to show a reduction at the three- and six-month follow-ups. In contrast, patients with mania had the biggest overall improvement at three months (54.0%), followed by those with psychotic depression (42.0%) and schizophrenia (14.8%), in terms of patients' cutoff points for diagnosis. Six months later, the proportion of patients who showed an improvement was as follows: mania (58.3%), psychotic depression (46.4%), and schizophrenia (30.7%) (Esen and Peters, 2023).

Nonetheless, Burns and Tomita (2015) observed that in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), a significant percentage of people seeking treatment for mental disorders consult traditional and religious healers in their pathway to mental health care. This is in their study *Traditional and religious healers in the pathway to care for people with mental disorders in Africa: a systematic review and meta-analysis*. The care pathway may be delayed as a result of healers' early involvement, which could be a barrier to early detection and intervention. However, this suggests that traditional and religious healers are unable to effectively treat mental illness, which may lead to patients and their loved ones looking for alternative—typically orthodox—forms of treatment (Burns and Tomita, 2015). Burns and Tomita further argued that since herbalists, diviners, and faith healers have all been identified as traditional and religious healers in this study, an understanding of the patronage of these healers in Nigeria and other African nations will help to clarify the patterns of health-seeking behavior among the mentally ill in these regions, which serves as the foundation for this study.

Sorsdahl *et al.* (2009) found that of the participants who sought treatment (regardless of whether they met lifetime DSM-IV criteria for a disorder or not), 21% were treated by Western practitioners, 13% by alternative practitioners, and 7% by a combination of both Western and alternative practitioners. The study examined the role of traditional healers in the treatment of common mental disorders in South Africa. Six percent of the participants who sought treatment from alternative medicine did so from a traditional healer, seven percent from a spiritual or religious advisor, and two percent from a different kind of healer. But only 2% of research participants exclusively sought treatment from a traditional healer, compared to 14% who sought treatment from a Western practitioner (Sorsdahl *et al.*, 2009).

In a study conducted in 2009 by Adewuya and Makanjuola titled *Preferred Treatment for Mental Illness Among Southwestern Nigerians*, the results revealed that 844 (41%) study participants chose spiritual healers as their preferred treatment option, compared to 634 (30%) who chose traditional healers and 600 (29%) who chose Western medicine. Additionally, they discovered that endorsement of supernatural causal beliefs, being a woman, having a lower level of education, and never having provided care for a person with mental illness were the factors that were independently associated with preference for spiritual or traditional healers. Subsequent examination of the data by Adewuya and Makanjuola (2009) revealed that there was no gender difference in the options available to traditional healers, with the majority of the gender difference being in the spiritual healers' category.

The majority of participants (76.8%) in Effiong and Albert's (2016) study, *Pathways to Psychiatric Care among Patients with Schizophrenia in Nigeria*, chose non-orthodox treatment facilities as their first choice for mental health assistance. According to the study, this

group includes (11.1%) of participants who saw traditional healers for the first time and (65.7%) of those who sought treatment from religious healers as their first point of contact. Prior to receiving care in a tertiary psychiatric facility, 41.7 percent of participants visited a second religious treatment center, and 36.8 percent visited a third, according to the study.

With 3.1 million members, or roughly 60% of the state's total population, the Ibibio tribe is the largest in Akwa Ibom State (Esen and Peters 2023^a). This is indicated by the fact that the tribe comprises about 16 of the state's 36 Local Government Areas (Esen and Peters, 2023^b). With their unique customs, culture, ethics, and more, the Ibibio are among the oldest ethnic groups in Nigeria, with a unique cultural heritage that spread across the Ibibio Local Government Area (Paul and Peters, 2023). The Ibibio people are renowned for their unique cultural belief in spirit beings and ancestors who live in the afterlife exactly as they did in this life, determine these. The belief also suggests that the spirit being has the ability to affect human affairs, such as health, the economy, and favour (Esen and Peters, 2023^b). Health issues are typically believed to be associated with offences against the deities, gods, and/or ancestors. In the cultural practice of health management in Ibibio land, the appeasement of the gods or deities is a necessity.

The symptoms one assumes or hears about are indicative of the nature of the illness. Youths have always characterised the largest population and are the driving force of our society (Peters, *et al*, 2022; Peters *et al*, 2023). Noticeable among the Ibibio people has been the fact that youths form the age cohort which is mostly affected by mental illness. This can be traced to the fact that youths are mostly involve in abusive consumption of psychoactive substances. According to Peters and Bassey (2020), youths in Akwa Ibom State especially in the riverine areas depend on one form or drug or the other for their daily activities like boat peddling, dragging of fishing nets and cutting of timbers.

Most often, divinity is invoked to aid in the diagnosis process. All of these are reliant on the Ibibio people's cultural heritage. Religion is a central theme in almost everything in Ibibio. It is believed that spiritual forces control everything from conception to childbirth, fertility, health, fortune, and even social influence (Oreva 2018). The Ibibio adage "*Obut isi mummo Idat ase omum eyeneka Idat*" (the shame of madness does not bother the mad person but his or her family members) indicates that mental illness is not foreign to Ibibio culture. The Ibibio people have made efforts to demystify the issue so that a permanent solution can be given to this illness, which is assumed to affect family members more than the mentally ill.

The lack of access to orthodox mental healthcare in Nigeria causes those who are mentally ill to look for other ways to get well. Gureje and Lasebikan (2006) noted that traditional, spiritual, faith-healing, and complementary medicine fill the service gap left by orthodox mental health practice in Nigeria. These practices are widely used in most communities because the general public's perception of mental disorders is still rooted in superstitious belief systems, particularly among the Ibibio people, and is therefore seen as incurable with western medicine. The present study aimed to bridge the existing gap in understanding the extent and rationale behind the Ibibio people's recourse to diviners as a mental health care alternative.

Source: Esen and Peters (2023^b)

The major components of MHSBM include;

Family of the patients: The family of the mentally ill person is the one who bear the burden of seeking treatment and healing for the said patient (their son/daughter).

Collective Perceived Threat: This refers to the consequences and cost (shame, disgrace, losses through violent behaviour of the patients, etc.), that the family stands to suffer if the said patient (their son/daughter) is not treated and restored to normal health or healed on time.

Collective Belief: This refers to the agreement of the family on a given choice of treatment based on the likely perceived benefits of the choice. This is also based on the level of availability of resources that the family will depend upon throughout the process of treating the said patient (their son/daughter).

Collective Behaviour: This refers to the response of the family toward the treatment/healing of the said patient (their son/daughter). This is based on the likely benefits that the family perceives in available treatment options, which is also based on the availability of resources that will enhance patronage of such available treatment options by the family.

Cue to Action: This refers to a readiness to take action toward the treatment of the said patient (their son/daughter).

METHODOLOGY

An ethnographic research design was adopted with a multi-stage type of data collection approach. The study area was Akwa Ibom state. Akwa Ibom is a state in Nigeria, created on the 23rd of September 1987, with Uyo as its capital. Akwa Ibom is one of Nigeria's 36 states, with a population of over five million people (NPC, 2006). The study was conducted among the Ibibio people of Akwa Ibom State. The Ibibio people are a coastal people in southern Nigeria (Cole and Derk, 2012). They are mostly found in Akwa Ibom State. They are related to the Anaang, Efik and Oron people. The Annang, Efik, and Oron share personal names, culture, and traditions with the Ibibio, and speak closely related varieties of Ibibio-Efik which are more or less mutually intelligible (Esen and Peters, 2023). The one local government area was selected from the three senatorial districts in Akwa Ibom State. Onna,

Etinan, and Ini Local Government Areas were selected for the study.

The researchers adopted a big-net approach (Fatterman, 2010) to gather information from the study participants. Participant observation, in-depth interview (II), key informant interview (KII), and focus group discussions (FGDs) were used by the researchers to obtain primary data. Secondary data were collected through published materials and internet sources.

RESULT

Divination Practice and knowing the cause of mental illness

Divination is the practice of consulting the spirit world in order to know the cause or causes of events or happenings within the traditional society. Diviners' consultation has been part of the cultural practices of the Ibibio people and has influenced their ways of life over generations. According to gathered information from discussions and interviews, the relevance of diviners is reducing across Ibibio land, and their functions have been taken over by the new dimension of the Christian movement especially the prayer house movement of Christianity. The majority of the study respondents agreed in their responses to the fact that divination is no longer relevant in the treatment of illness since people are more interested in solutions than getting to know the source of their illnesses or who is behind their problems.

A study participant aged 48 years in his response to an interview said;

We are no longer interested in who is responsible for our problems or sickness because we have heard enough from all these prophets and prophetesses neither are we interested in knowing the source of any problem or sickness. All we are now looking for are solutions to our diverse problems and healing to our sicknesses (Male, 48 years, interviewed on 22/8/2019).

Mental illness is a health condition that forces everyone around the patient to focus on a solution instead of concentrating on the source of the illness. Gathered information revealed that it is only on rare occasions that people care to know who is responsible for or the source of the mental condition of their relatives. One of the key informants from Ikot Okpudo in Nsit Ubium Local Government Area, in his responses, said;

People are not really interested in knowing who is responsible for their problems, what they are really after is solutions, if they can get the solution, they easily forget about how it happened, what they have passed through while trying to get to the solution, talk more of source or who is responsible. Their joy especially in the case of madness is always so much that they will not want to know any other thing. It has been only on very rare occasion right from the days of my father till today that someone will want to know who is responsible for the mental health condition of their relative (Male, 38 years, interview conducted on 24/8/2019).

Though interest in divination is fading away among the Ibibio people in Akwa Ibom State due to the influence of Christianity, study participants revealed that very few persons on

special demands do request divination services in knowing what and who is/are responsible for the problem. A key informant from Nkwot Etok in Ini Local Government Area said;

Well, I have been in this practice for many years, people have brought their patients to me from far and near, I have treated them, and they do recover but only on special requests have I seen a few persons ask to know in form of consulting the office of the diviner priest, and I collect from them what I have to collect and consult for them. I told them who was responsible and why those who plotted the evil against me wanted to get out of their brothers' madness (Male, 50 years, interview conducted on 26/8/2019).

Divination has not been a treatment method for mental illness among the Ibibio, but a way to discover or inquire about the source or who is responsible for a particular mental illness. Information gathered from the participants revealed that divination practice is in most cases combined by traditional herbalists. The office of divination is always consulted for inquiry of the ancestors of gods. Christianity has greatly reduced the influence of divination and the relevance of diviners.

Divination Practice and Seeking control of the spirit of madness

Seeking to know which spirit is responsible for the mental illness among the people is one of the reasons Ibibio people consult diviners as gathered by the data through interviews. Narratives revealed that behind seeking to know what spirit is responsible is the aim of seeking control of such spirit. Study participants agreed through interviews and discussion that many people especially relatives of mentally ill persons do seek to control the spirits that are responsible for the mental illness in order to see how to rescue their victims from the forces of such spirits. One of the study participants in her narratives reported that;

We believe that madness or mental sickness is controlled by the spirit. In fact, whenever anybody has a mental problem these evil spirits will come into such a person and overtake the person. You can remember in the Bible that the mad man that Jesus healed by casting out legions was a lesson to us that spirits are responsible for madness and Jesus was able to control these spirits. So most of our people...ah, ah, ah, including me, oh, we believe that spirits are responsible for madness and to cure madness you have to control the spirits. That is why our people patronize these diviners for help (Female, 46 years, trader, interviewed on 17/9/2023).

Observations from fieldwork show that most of the mentally ill persons are forced under control in order to subject them to treatments. Diviners are specialist in controlling the mentally ill person and subject such to treatment. One of the key informant who is a specialist as a diviner in treating mental illness in his narratives said that;

I have been in this business since I was a young boy with my late father who was in-charge before he handed over to me just before his death. I was taught that the only way you can treat a violent mad man or what you call mental sick person is to control him or her,

else you cannot treat the person. This is because the person will not collect such thing as medicine from you. Sometimes the spirit will not allow the person to collect anything that can give the person relieve from the power of madness. So, my father taught me how to use this grass called “*Mkpa tatad*“ which is has a tiny rod and I will tie them with the robe from the grass and they will be calm and the spirit will be controlled and the person will be subjected to treatment. There was a time they brought a young man with chains to me and when they pulled him out of the car and he saw me, he started screaming and tore the chains into pieces and wanted to run away, but because I always have *mkpa tatad* with me, I quickly rush and flog him with the grass and he began to beg and be calm. Else, he would have ran away and the family will not see him again. But, thank God, today he is normal because he was healed and returned home to his family (Male, 58 years, interview conducted on 26/8/2019)

Divination has been a cultural practice in African Traditional Medicine (ATR) where its major practice is for the control and consultation of the spirits. In the case of mental illness, divination has played great role by diviners who through this mean have claimed to have treated many mentally ill person who were free from the illness. Among the Ibibio people, divination is one of the major means of seeking treatment and other solutions to man's problems.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

On general knowledge about mental illness, findings show that Ibibio people consider mental illness to be caused by spiritual forces which create the basis for high level of diviners' consultation. There is a high level of belief that some spiritual forces are responsible for mental illness. This situation and belief system greatly affects the mental health seeking behaviour of the Ibibio people in Akwa Ibom State. On choice of treatment for mental illness, finding's show that since Ibibio people believe that mental illness is spiritually controlled, the first and best choice of treatment as revealed through discussions and interviews is faith healing or traditional herbalist which are normal practiced in combination with divination and the services are always provided by diviners or people with the gift of divination, who will be able to deal with the spirits in order to deliver the mentally ill persons. Credence to this finding is gotten from Kabir *et al* (2004) who posit that community attitude and beliefs, play a role in determining help-seeking behaviour and successful treatment of the mentally ill.

Findings on consultation of diviners for mental illness among Ibibio people revealed that though diviners' consultation has been a long-standing cultural practice of the Ibibio people, the majority of the people do not patronize diviners for mental health care or cure. The reasons for poor patronage of diviners for mental illness according to the findings include; a lack of interest in knowing the source of the mental problem or who is responsible since solution is paramount, and the services of diviners have been taken over by the prophets and prophetesses of some of the churches and prayer houses found within Ibibio land. Ahmed *et al* (2015) confirmed this finding by stating that certain aspects of the cultural practices of the

society, which are entrenched in the way people think, reason, act, and speak influence their reason for health-seeking behaviour. Further findings showed that most of the traditional herbalists combine herbs and roots with divination. On very rare occasions very few persons have consulted the office of the diviners for anything in relation to the mental problems of their relatives. A key reason for poor patronage of orthodox treatments for mental illness is that the majority of people consider mental illness to be a spiritual case rather than physical.

CONCLUSION

The main objective of this study was to investigate divination patronage as an alternative mental health seeking behaviour of Ibibio people in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Mental illness to the Ibibio people is spiritually controlled ailment which needs spiritual intervention for the control of the spirit toward successful and effective treatment. The most preferred treatment for mental illness among the Ibibio people is the spiritualist's treatment which is always practiced by diviners though the majority of them engage faith healing practice and traditional herbalist treatments. There is high degree of stigmatization among the Ibibio people in Akwa Ibom State in relation to mental illness. Diviners play key roles in controlling the spirits of madness in order to subject the mentally ill person to treatment. Out of fear of stigmatization, a lot of people have chosen to take their mentally ill patients to diviners especially those who combine divination with faith healing, and herbal treatment. This practice has positioned a lot of Ibibio people in diviners' patronage and poor patronage of psychiatric hospital.

RECOMMENDATION

Base on the findings of the study, the researchers make the following recommendations;

1. More psychiatric hospitals should be built across the Ibibio speaking local government areas to match the rising number of mentally ill persons.
2. Government and non-government organizations should embark on proper education of the people on the causes of mental illness in order to replace or reduce the degree of belief that mental illness is a spiritual problem.
3. The people should be enlightened on the likely actions to be taken immediately if there is observation of signs of mental illness among the people.
4. Faith healers and traditional herbalists should be supported and formally registered for proper monitoring and control by the government in order to reposition them for better service delivery, and efficient contribution in tackling the menace of mental illness in society.

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